

Effect of Net Working Capital on the Corporate Cash Holdings of Commercial Banks in Kenya

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Abstract: An effective and efficient net working capital majorly contribute to commercial banks success as it forms part of a company's short-term financing strategy. Efficiency of working capital is based on the principle of speeding up collections as quickly as possible and slowing down disbursements as slowly as possible. An effective working capital management system helps banks not only cover their financial obligations but also boost their earnings. The study sought to examine the effects of working capital which comprised of aspects current assets and current liabilities. This study is guided by two theories, namely; Free Cash Flow Hypothesis and the Agency theory. The study adopted the descriptive and explanatory research designs. The population of the current study comprised of all commercial banks thus a census survey method was adopted. This study relied on secondary data which was obtained from annual reports issued by the CBK Bank. The results of the study showed that there was positive linear relationship between net working capital and the dependent variable (corporate cash holding) and the model was statistically significant. The study used ANOVA to establish the significance of the regression model from which an f-significance value of p less than 0.05 was established. The findings of the analysis revealed that when the independent variables had a significant combined effect ($R^2 = 0.428$) on corporate cash holding in the commercial banks in Kenya and could be used to predict future profitability. The study concludes that Net working capital has a significant relationship with cash held by commercial banks while Changes in banks characteristics over time are primarily responsible for the increase in cash holdings and therefore net working capital of firms drastically decreases and cash flows become riskier. It was recommended that the financial managers should focus on reducing the cash conversion cycle by investing more in net working capital.

Keywords: *Corporate Cash Holdings, Net Working Capital, Commercial Banks.*

I. Background of the study

Working capital refers to all actions and decisions that influences the size and efficiency of the working capital that is used in maintaining the optimal balance of current liabilities such as accounts payables and current assets including cash, accounts receivables and inventory. Incorrect working capital models is likely to decrease the return ratio of a firm and therefore cause its insolvency. Banks employ both the current assets and liabilities in their day to day operations to generate economic profit for the interests of all stakeholders. As such, for commercial banks to have going concern, optimum liquidity should be maintained with neither excessive nor inadequate working capital (Velnampy & Niresh, 2012).

The financial system in Kenya is organized according to conventional lines. Managing working capital is a core activity which is also a daily process that requires bank managers to monitor and project cash-flows (Kesimli & Gunay, 2011). Sathamoorathi (2002) asserts that; an increase in current asset to total asset leads to a negative effect on profitability, while an increase in current liabilities to total liabilities gives a positive effect on profitability.

Kenya Commercial banks play a major role in contributing to economic growth by making funds available for investors to borrow as well as financial deepening (Ojala, 2012). Cash is a vital asset for commercial banks as it is one of the most significant figures found within the assets portion in the statement of their financial position. Cash offers any corporation with liquidity and facilitates payment of various types of financial obligations.

With insufficient liquid assets, a company will not have the ability to meet those obligations hence forced to declare bankruptcy status. Cash holdings are commonly defined as cash and marketable securities or cash equivalents (Opler, 1999). Cash equivalents consist of current assets which can be converted into cash in a very short term and are thus characterized by a high degree of liquidity (Ferreira & Vilela, 2004). As such, it is predictable that adequate net working capital is positively related to corporate cash holdings of the commercial banks in Kenya.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Commercial banks success is determined majorly by the ability of financial managers to effectively manage the components of working capital. The Finance managers are obligated to lessen to a great extent the current assets and protract current expenses. Majority of the Kenya commercial banks do not maintain optimal working capital which negatively impacts their profitability maximization objective thus creating liquidity issues. There hence exists a knowledge gap when it comes to the drivers of corporate liquidity. Under the pressure of weak equity markets, rising financing costs, liquidity problems, and record-high volatility in markets, many commercial banks must proceed to rethink the way a firm's net working capital structure is managed. Therefore, this study was conducted to fill this gap by investigating the effect of net working capital on the corporate cash holdings of commercial banks in Kenya.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no statistically significant effect of net working capital on the corporate cash holdings of commercial banks in Kenya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2 Theoretical Review

This section presents the theories on which the study is anchored. This study is guided by two theories, namely; Free Cash Flow Hypothesis and the Agency theory.

2.2.1 Free Cash Flow Hypothesis

Free Cash Flow hypothesis is credited with Jensen (1986). The theory objects to the existence of target cash levels. The theory states that consumption of private benefits by managers, and in turn, the agency conflicts between managers and shareholders, is expected to be larger in firms operating in industries with limited growth opportunities and are generating large amounts of free cash flows. According to Harford (1999), since cash holdings are used to serve management's own interest at the expense of the shareholders, they are perceived as free cash flows. Therefore, the free cash flow hypothesis suggests that firms are inclined to cash stock up because it increases the assets under their control. With the cash stockpile, the managers would easily avoid the capital markets thus not complying with transparency requirements on possible investments.

2.2.2 Agency Theory

The agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. The agency theory indicates that the daily operations of a firm are handled by managers who act on behalf of the owners (shareholders) with both having different expectations. The major problem associated with this theory includes information asymmetry, moral hazard and adverse selection (Kwame, 2010).

The agency theory postulates that the day to day running of a commercial bank should be carried out by financial managers as the agents who have been engaged by the owners of the business as principals who are also known as shareholders. The major problem associated with this theory includes information asymmetry, moral hazard and adverse selection (Kwame, 2010).

2.3 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework consists of broad ideas and principles that are taken from relevant fields of enquiry and used to structure a subsequent presentation (Kombo & Tromp, 2009.) The study conceptual framework showed the independent (networking capital) and dependent variables (Corporate cash Holding) of the study which were

correlated. Working capital, also known as net working capital or NWC, was calculated as current assets minus current liabilities. The major components of working capital are accounts receivable, inventories, cash and cash equivalents and accounts payable. Therefore, the changes in net working capital affect the cash holdings. Besides, the changes in short-term debt could be a substitute for cash, because firms may use short-term debt as financial resource. The more efficient the firm is in managing its working capital, the less the requirements for external financing and the better financial performance. The objective of net working capital management (WCM) was to minimize the cost of maintaining liquidity while guarding against the risk of insolvency, working capital policy applies to short-term decisions, and capital structure finance applies to long-term decisions.

Independent variable

Dependent variable

Fig. 2.1 Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a multimethod research design. According to Mingers (2003), use of multimethod research design produces richer and more reliable results. The study therefore adopted the descriptive and explanatory research designs. According to Cooper and Schindler (2011), descriptive study is used to describe or define, often by way of profiling a group of problems, people or events through data collection and tabulation of frequencies research variables or their interactions. According to Rahi (2017), explanatory research establishes and explains a situation or problem in the form of causal relationships between variables under study.

3.2 Target Population

According to Ngechu (2006), a population is a complete set of individuals, cases, or objects with some common observable characteristics. A particular population has unique characteristics differentiating it from other population. Ngechu (2006) further indicates that a target population is a group of individuals, event or objects which a researcher wants to generalize the findings. The population of the current study comprised of all commercial banks registered and licensed to operate in Kenya as at 31st December 2017.

3.3 Sampling and Sampling Techniques

Cooper and Schindler (2011) reported that sampling refers to the selection of a proportionate representation from the total population under study. It enables to lower cost, give accuracy of results, and increase speed of data collection and availability of population elements. According to Collins and Hussey (2009), sampling technique is a method of selecting elements from a study population that will represent the entire population. This study adopted a census survey method where all the commercial banks were analyzed. This sampling technique was chosen because the units of analysis are few.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments and procedure

This study heavily relied on secondary data which was obtained from annual reports issued by the CBK Bank Supervision unit. The researcher used the data collection sheet where all the variables were entered after extraction from the financial statements of the banks. This was followed by a data summarization and subsequent data cleaning to ensure that data is ready for analysis.

3.5 Data Analysis

The relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables were determined by use of regression analysis. The data was prepared and analyzed using Microsoft (MS) Excel and SPSS. A ten-year (2008-2017) panel data was considered in the study. The regression model which was adopted was as follows:

$$Y_{it} = c + \beta_2 NWC_{it} + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y_{it} - is the Corporate Cash Holding of firm i in period t as measured by the ratio of total cash and cash equivalents to total assets.

NWC_{it} is net working capital of firm i in period t .

c - Constant of regression.

ϵ - is error term of the regression model.

Coefficients are the regression coefficients as determined by the model. The coefficients was determined through estimation using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethics refers to a system of principles which can critically change previous considerations about choices and actions. Ethics are norms or standards of behaviour that guide moral choices about our behavior and our relationships with others, and as such all parties in research should exhibit ethical behavior. (Saunders et al., 2003). Privacy of respondents, voluntary participation and the right to withdraw, consent and the possible deception of participants, maintenance of confidentiality of data provided by individuals or identified participants and their anonymity (Mathooko, et al., 2011).

One of the major ethical consideration in this study was deception where data was collected with a full disclosure that it would be used for academic purposes only. Openness and honesty were observed in the course of collecting and analyzing the data. Ethical considerations in the present study were adhered to accordingly including acquiring a Research Permit from the National Commission for Science Technology and Innovation and adhering to its terms conditions and requirements. These aspects-built value to the study and bolstered its reliability and validity

IV. DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Correlation Analysis between Net Working Capital and Corporate Cash Holding

A correlation is a bivariate analysis that measures the strength of association between two variables and the direction of the relationship. In terms of the strength of relationship, the value of the correlation coefficient varies between +1 and -1. A correlation coefficient statistic that describes the degree of linear association between Net Working Capital and Corporate Cash Holding was determined.

Table 1: Correlation between Net Working Capital and Corporate Cash Holding

		Net working capital	Corporate cash holding
Net working capital	Pearson Correlation	1	.235
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	40	40
Corporate cash holding	Pearson Correlation	.235	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	40	40

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation results indicates that there is a positive significant linear relationship between net working capital levels and corporate cash holding of commercial banks in Kenya. This relationship has been illustrated by correlation coefficient of 0.235 at 0.01 significant level. This implies that there is a positive and significant relationship between net working capital levels and corporate cash holding and as such indicated that low investment in current assets and low current liabilities financing increases the corporate cash holding of commercial banks in Kenya.

4.2 Regression analysis between Net Working Capital and Corporate Cash Holding

A regression analysis was used to assess whether predictor variables accounted for variability in a dependent variable. Regression analysis was conducted to determine the amount of variation in corporate cash holding explained by working capital levels.

Table 2: Model Summary for net Working Capital Levels

R	R Square	Adj R Square	Std. Error Of The Estimate
0.459	.428	.398	3.3959

The calculated R – value was 0.459. R² value was 0.428 which means that 42.8% of the corresponding variation in holding corporate cash profitability can be explained by net working capital levels. The rest 57.2% can be explained by other factors that are not in the model.

4.3. Beta Coefficients

The beta coefficient is the degree of change in the outcome variable for every 1-unit of change in the predictor variable. The *t*-test assessed whether the beta coefficient was significantly different from zero. If the beta coefficient is positive, the interpretation is that for every 1-unit increase in the predictor variable, the outcome variable will increase by the beta coefficient value. A standardized beta coefficient was used to compares the strength of the effect of independent variable to the dependent variable. The higher the absolute value of the beta coefficient, the stronger the effect.

Table3. Beta Coefficients Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	0.117	.187		0.631	.536
Net Working Capital	0.156	.043	.258	2.678	.037

- a) Predictors: (Constant), Net Working Capital
- b) Dependent Variable: Corporate cash holdings

The coefficients results showed that Net Working Capital, the regression coefficient is positive (0.156) indicating that the more ideal level of Corporate cash holdings, the higher the of the commercial banks and the relationship is statistically significant (*p* = 0.000). A unit increase in corporate cash holdings would lead to a 0.156 increase in net working capital. The *t* – values confirmed that Net Working Capital, is a useful predictor of effectiveness of Corporate cash holdings (*t* = 2.678).

V. CONCLUSIONS

Net working capital affects corporate cash holdings of the commercial banks. A negative and significant relationship between net working capital and leverage to cash holding exist. Net working capital has a significant relationship with cash held by commercial banks. With insufficient internally generated cash, a Bank cannot obtain external financing at fair prices without compromising corporate growth and investments. Changes in firm characteristics over time are primarily responsible for the increase in cash holdings and therefore net working capital of firms drastically decreases and cash flows become riskier.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The financial managers should focus more on reducing the number of days in inventory and accounts receivable and shortening the cash conversion cycle which also improves the bank’s profitability. This will help maintain the inventory at optimal level and thus reduce the costs of holding inventory. The managers should also focus on reducing the cash conversion cycle by investing more in working capital.

VII. SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

It is recommend that the effect of working capital management be evaluated for a wider scope of SME’s and listed commercial banks. This way, a researcher can do a comparison of findings after which a comprehensive and reliable conclusion can be drawn. Alternatively, future research should re-apply the current study in the future with a focus on a different period of time.

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